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Research Article

Mathematical formula of sex, love, economy and happiness. Therapy and psychiatric analysis of the economy and the financial markets

Abstract

Economics, financial markets are sciences that try to predict the behavior of actors to get the best performance possible, however, in general economic analyzes are made on scientific and logical mathematical rules, rational, and this is extremely important and the Key to everything, since the entities that interact in the market are human beings, and human beings present illogical and irrational psychic devices, this may explain in part why it is so difficult to predict the behavior of the markets, resulting in low yields Or in some cases gigantic economic losses. Long-term deposits tend to generate higher interest dividends since the inability of depositors to take their money immediately and when they require it increases their levels of anxiety, distress, so the reward and gratification has to be greater, stronger psychic devices will tend to save more and savings will be long term, while individuals with weak psychic devices will tend to save less and deposits will be in current accounts.

Introduction

Economics, financial markets are sciences that try to predict the behavior of actors to get the best performance possible, however, in general economic analyzes are made on scientific and logical mathematical rules, rational, and this is extremely important and the Key to everything, since the entities that interact in the market are human beings, and human beings present illogical and irrational psychic devices, this may explain in part why it is so difficult to predict the behavior of the markets, resulting in low yields Or in some cases gigantic economic losses (Figure 1).

I shall now outline the most important statement of all, or at least one of the most important, pay close attention to what I am going to raise: The meaning of life is to feed to survive and happiness is to have sex. I need money to feed myself and therefore to have sex. So the statement goes like this: I need money to have sex, all human beings generate wealth to have sex, satisfying the sexual drive is all that matters in life. Sex is the basis of the entire world economy, financial markets and is the only thing that matters and gives meaning to life.

Now, many of you will have heard this before, however the mathematical application of these statements in human behavior are quite complex to put into practice in economic

analysis. First they have to understand that what they read as sex, actually refers to the discharge of the sexual drive. The discharge of the sexual instinct can be satisfied in many ways, so it is not easy to predict how the instinct will be discharged, and not how the psychic apparatus will be satisfied.

In the image it explain a little about the psychic aparatus.

The structural model of the psychic apparatus is composed of three different psychic structures: 1) the: it is the most important to understand in my opinion to be able to predict economic behavior. The id is purely unconscious, it has the drives, the drives are a kind of energy that determines the will, there may be erotic and tanatic drives. The erotic drives are

Figure 1: The figure shows how the unconscious Id tries to download the sex drive so that the person can be happy, and superego represses preventing the person to have sex every day, several times a day resulting in pain, suffering, anxiety, depression.

those concerning love, affection, tenderness, construction, sex, in such a way that the id is responsible for generating wealth and money in trying to satisfy the discharge of the sexual drive, sex costs money and therefore makes All to make money, to make money is to be able to have sex the only thing that matters in life. Then I will develop the idea.

The tanatic drives (death) are violent, aggression, death, destruction. We need these violent and aggressive tanatic drives to defend ourselves against predators, if our psychic apparatus lacked these violent impulses, we would not have been able to survive as a species. Then I will detail the importance of tanatic drives in the economy and how they are involved in generating profits and losses.

2) The other component of the psychic apparatus is the superego. The superego has a consensual and an unconscious portion. It is constituted by the ethical and moral norms and rules of society, our parents, religion, laws, state prosecutorial organs, court of justice, and its executing agencies such as security agencies, police, armed forces, etc. The function of the superego is to suppress and frustrate the impulses of the id. It frustrates both the tanatic and the erotic drives. So the superego tends to repress, frustrate and avoid the download of the drives of the id, if it wants to satisfy itself and discharge its sexual drive, the super-ego will prevent it from doing so it prevents people from losing money but also Tends to prevent them from gaining it. Then develop the idea in economic predictions.

3) The third component of the psychic apparatus is the Self, has a conscious and an unconscious portion. Its function is to mediate the conflict that is generated between the id and the superego, if the self is not strong enough to stabilize the conflict will appear the symptom, in this case economic problems. Then I will develop the idea [1,2].

Now, why do humans need money? Simple and most important of all: Humans need money for sex. In reality human beings do not need money, money did not exist in primitive societies, but the social dynamics worked differently, money was not necessary because hunting, fishing, gathering food was enough to survive, so that as the resources were virtually unlimited, there was no need to generate wealth and development to satisfy the basic psychodynamic drives like having sex. Unless it was quality sex, We'll talk about it later. With the increase of the population, resources became more and more limited, so there was not enough for everyone and therefore there was a cost and sacrifice for subsistence, that's when the suffering began.

With unlimited economic resources the availability of sex was almost unlimited as well, yet there was a key drive for economic prosperity and development, although sex was readily available, quality sex has always been very limited. Quality sex is having sex with a healthy woman. Now you are wondering, what is a healthy woman? a healthy woman is a physically attractive woman. The physical attractiveness is synonymous of health, therefore the men look for the healthiest women, that is to say the most physically attractive to have their offspring. This guarantees greater probability of passing the genetic load to future generations.

Another of the fundamental characteristics of sex is frequency. Although in some conditions sex is relatively free, at no cost, that happens only with a low frequency, the sexual frequency in men is much greater than that of women, the man can have sex several times a day and fertilize several women a day, while women only need to have sex once every nine months during their reproductive stage, consequently the supply of sex by women is much lower biologically to the demand of sex by men , So that the cost and the price of sex increases enormously, this will cause men to have to produce money and wealth to be able to satisfy their psychic devices through the discharge of their sexual drives.

As we have the quality and quantity of sex as fundamental biological mechanisms in human beings that generate wealth and money, we will take this into account later to analyze the economic behavior of human beings. But basically they must understand that men need sex the greatest number of times a day, with the most attractive women possible, the demand for sex is high in men, the supply of sex is low in quantity and quality by women and this increases the price and cost of sex, so it takes high productivity, competition and economic efficiency to meet the biological needs of sex on humanity.

In the case of women, anthropologically they did not need to produce money or wealth since the basic necessities of life were provided by men, and only a small percentage of women had to produce money and wealth to satisfy their basic needs, the limitation of resources, man's work is no longer enough even to satisfy the basic needs of men, much less that of women, much less that of children or family, so that women have had to leave generate money and wealth to meet their basic needs.

Another important element of the generation of wealth by women is that men seek sex of quality and quantity, so that only the most attractive women will have a better quality of life, since men with greater wealth will be willing to give them, however, less attractive women need generate money and wealth [3].

But what does a woman need money for? In reality, women do not need money or wealth, they only need to cover their basic needs for survival (food), however the greater the accumulation of capital and wealth by women, their offspring will have more chances of survival and therefore genetic legacy is more likely to perpetuate itself in time, which is one of the basic drives of human beings.

What do men need money for? In reality men do not need money, neither wealth nor capital, they only need the minimum to satisfy their basic subsistence needs (food), however the more money, more wealth or capital the man has, the greater his probability of having sex of quantity and quality, more women and more physically attractive, which is synonymous with health in women, so that their offspring will have more possibility to survive and perpetuate its genetic legacy, which is the most important psychodynamic drive in the humans.

So in general formula we have that women want money, in such a way that they themselves have to produce more money and or make men produce more money, wealth and capital

to satisfy the psychodynamic drives of men and women. So the discharge of psychodynamic drives is determined only by money. So money is the most important means of our psychic apart in our society.

Is money the most important thing for women? No, actually the most biologically important thing is the health of genetic offspring, so physical attractiveness in men is the most important thing that women should consider. Physical attractiveness is synonymous with health in men, making it the most relevant factor. However, with limited food resources, the man who has the most money, wealth and capital to provide basic needs will be the most quoted in women's markets. Now in the complex society in which we live is not the strongest but the most apt one who has the best chances of surviving, so the complexity of society generates that men with wealth, capital, money, but unattractive in the women's markets.

Women can have sex and get pregnant by physically attractive and healthy men and make men believe with wealth, money and capital are the parents being this lie, but it is a little risky, especially at present with genetic diagnostic methods to determine the biological parents. Men generally refuse to raise children who do not possess their genetic load, so it has always been risky for women.

Another fact to consider is that physical attractiveness is synonymous with health, but it is also synonymous with better conditions, attitudes in humans, at least genetically and innate. I explain, men look for attractive women, women by social complexity seek men with money (which are the most attractive in general) so that genetic exchange will generate physically attractive children with social skills to generate money (intelligence of any kind, usually social). Through many generations with a mixture of physical attractiveness and capacities to generate wealth, money and capital will generate human beings with capacities to generate wealth, money, capital and that will be the most physically attractive. While the less physically attractive people will be those who have less genetic predisposition to generate money and wealth.

Unattractive people can not physically generate wealth? Yes, physically unattractive people can generate wealth, money and capital, even more than physically attractive people, only they will have less genetic predisposition for it.

Do humans only need sex and food to survive? If, in fact, the idea that we are evolutionary rational beings are inadequate interpretations of the behavior of human beings, I will not enter into philosophical considerations here, but for centuries Galileo took away as the center of the universe, Darwin took away as the last end of the living beings and established that we were simply the product of the chance of evolution, Einstein completely erased the objective temporality of the universe argued by philosophers for thousands of years, and as Nietzsche said: Sigmund Freud would finish killing God, evidencing that we are actually beings Irrational like any other, that we have practically no capacity of free will, and that our unconscious determines all our behavior in the world. An unconscious that is irrational, illogical, timeless, unpredictable and very difficult

to interpret and understand. However, despite the fact that not all human beings show a predictable and homogeneous behavior, we will say that 80% of humans behave with these fundamental principles.

1) Men need food to survive and want sex to perpetuate their genetic legacy. They need money, capital and wealth to obtain sex as often as possible and of the best possible quality, that is to say with the most attractive women possible (since physical attractiveness is synonymous with health) in this way their offspring will present more probabilities of survival.

2) Women need food to survive and want sex, much less often than men, so women's sex supply decreases, which increases the price of sex, they also want the sex of the highest quality possible (with attractive men physically, synonymous with health and with the greatest wealth, capital and money possible) which increases the probability of survival of their offspring.

3) Approximately 20% of the population does not enter the previous categories, their psychic apparatus does not behave like the majority of the population, in such a way that they do not want sex (abstainers for example), or reject food to survive (anorexia or bulimia for example), even if they have erotic impulses of love, construction, tenderness, affection, which generate wealth, capital and money, they present tanatic drives of hatred, violence, destruction, death, which destroy wealth, money and capital. Another important fact of this type of people is that they can be in any institution of the society (politics, financial sector, industries) and generate economic disasters, the other important fact of this percentage of the population is that they are difficult to diagnose and can infiltrate In the highest spheres of power without anyone knowing it until the disasters happen and it is too late. Tanatic drives can be against others and also against themselves, so that the logic of self-protection where each person seeks their best benefit is not met for them, and unconsciously can attempt against themselves lose money, go to jail or even die as them unconscious desire.

Is the psychic apparatus satisfied with sex only? No, the psychic apparatus is satisfied by discharging unconscious psychodynamic drives, such as sex, or violence if the drive is tanatic, yet almost all women repress the discharge of unconscious psychodynamic drives so that they have no sex, or have it with very low frequency, remember that women only need to have sex 1 time every 9 months during their reproductive age, so the supply of sex by women is much lower than the demand of men who want to have sex all the days several times a day. This disproportion between the supply and demand of sex generates that sex prices increase enormously, forcing the increase of productivity, generation of money, wealth and capital.

An important fact to keep in mind is that women repress the discharge of the psychodynamic drives of the psychic apparatus such as sex, this repression occurs through a structure of the psychic apparatus called superego, however repression generates a lot of pain, anxiety, depression and suffering in women, so they have to attenuate that pain

with various psychodynamic defense mechanisms such as sublimation. Sublimation refers to replacing the ultimate end of the discharge of the sexual drive for another purpose, such as art, music, painting, sculpture, writing, etc., can also try to fill the original lack of sexual desire by means of material possessions such as jewelry, cars, houses, travel, money, luxuries.

The fundamental problem with replacing the discharge of the sexual instinct with material possessions is that, just as the satisfaction generated by the discharge of the sexual drive is temporary, so they will constantly need to accumulate more and more material possessions in an infinite way to keep their appeased the lack, the suffering, the anxiety, the depression that generates the desire.

The superego of women repress the discharge of the sexual drive, so despite having to have sex 1 time every 9 months of reproductive age, repression further decreases sexual frequency and can spend a lot of time without discharging the sexual drives, so that the supply of sex by women decreases even more which increases the pressure of sex much more, which generates greater development, production, capital, wealth, money on the part of men to satisfy their unconscious sexual psychodynamic impulses .

Anxiety, anguish and panic in financial systems and capital markets. Anxiety and panic determine behavior in individuals in financial systems and capital markets.

Having money is equal to having sex, so the loss of money involves the loss of sex, this is what generates anxiety, anguish and panic in the population. We will develop this idea later.

Anxiety, anxiety and panic in banking systems

In the banking system the collective management of anxiety is fundamental, since depending on the legislation in different countries and that governments demand the percentage of compulsory deposits, the cash that they have to keep available for deposit takers' withdrawals varies between 10 and 20%, if massive withdrawals of money from depositors occurred the banks could not respond to the demands and would collapse the entire financial system. Much worse than the panic of all depositors, it would suffice that a single bank does not have liquidity so that the anguish will infect the entire population and generate the chain reaction to the rest of the depositors of all banks. The banking system has mechanisms to prevent the spread of widespread panic. That mechanism to control anxiety and generalized panic is backed by the central bank, if any of the banks are insolvent, or have no liquidity, the central bank supports that insolvency and that illiquidity through the printing of money, print money and returns it to depositors, however the impression of money generates devaluation so the mechanism of controlling anxiety is not completely effective, that potential loss and partial depositors money, the anguish remains permanently in the apparatus of people (Figures 2-5).

Current accounts or long-term deposits

Long-term deposits tend to generate higher interest dividends since the inability of depositors to take their money

immediately and when they require it increases their levels of anxiety, distress, so the reward and gratification has to be greater, stronger psychic devices will tend to save more and savings will be long term, while individuals with weak psychic devices will tend to save less and deposits will be in current accounts.

Anxiety, anguish and panic in the stock markets

There are several reasons why individuals prefer to have their money in stock markets instead of having them in the bank, as we have already studied having money in banks is relatively safe, however the less risk is that something happens to the money from individuals, the lower the return it

Figure 5: The figure shows how the woman puts her libido or libidinal energy (red line) on multiple objects: that means having casual sex with several men simultaneously libidinal energy puts on job, family, friends, pets, hobbies, exercises, happiness despite being partial, at least it is stable over time and there is less risk of generating depression, anxiety, pain and suffering. It is also the fastest way to remove the libidinal charge that has put on the couple abandoned or cheated.

generates, in some countries the interest rates are zero or even negative, so having the money in the bank is relatively safe but does not generate interest and even in some cases it costs money to have deposits in banks. While putting money in the stock markets increases the risk of losing money, but equally increases profitability.

There are some interesting considerations that we have to make when analyzing the stock markets, they basically behave like a casino, people can make lots of money and also lose everything in a short time, without laws or mathematical rules of logic involved in the process. This is very interesting since the unconscious psychic apparatus behaves in this way, illogical, without mathematical rules that can explain it.

To analyze the behavior of individuals in casinos we will talk about impulse control disorder, gambling belongs to this group of disorders, where the individual has a drive in this case is pathological gambling and is unable to control the drive of gambling, since the mathematical probability of losing in a casino is much greater than that of winning, gambling has a self-destructive component, the individual wants to unconsciously lose all his money in the casino or in the stock markets and be completely ruined and destroyed.

In gambling, other unconscious psychodynamic impulses are satisfied; during the activity of pathological gambling the psychic apparatus is performing a psychomotor activity, that fact alone is a disperser of anxiety. Likewise the uncertainty of possibility of winning or losing releases chemical mediators in the central nervous system like dopamine which produces a stimulus of reward. In general, pathological gambling is carried out in legal or illegal casinos where there is consumption of alcohol and other people so it partially satisfies and fills the subject's original lack of anxiety.

The drives that determine the pathological gambling in the casinos and the stock markets are for all the actors involved so much for the direct investors that put their money there as for the intermediaries like broker, brokers of bag etc. They

may also present impulse control disorder, self-destructive impulses and personality disorders, such as psychopathic personality disorder, consciously or unconsciously generating fraud, scams, bankruptcies.

Criteria for the diagnosis of pathological gambling

A. Behavior of adaptive, persistent and recurrent game, as indicated by at least five (or more) of the following items:

1. concern about gambling (eg, concern about reliving past gaming experiences, clearing advantages between competitors or planning the next adventure, or thinking about ways to get money to play with)
2. need to play with increasing amounts of money to get the desired degree of excitement
3. repeated failure of efforts to control, interrupt or stop the game
4. restlessness or irritability when attempting to interrupt or stop play
5. play is used as a strategy to escape from problems or to alleviate dysphoria (eg, feelings of hopelessness, guilt, anxiety, depression)
6. After losing money in the game, it becomes another day to try to recover it (trying to "hunt" the losses themselves)
7. Family members, therapists, or other people are tricked into concealing the degree of involvement with the game
8. illegal acts, such as forgery, fraud, theft, or abuse of trust, are committed to finance gambling
9. have risked or lost significant interpersonal relationships, work and educational or professional opportunities due to gambling
10. trust that others will provide money to ease the desperate financial situation caused by gambling

B. Game behavior is not best explained by the presence of a manic episode.

Because the individual wants to lose all his money, to be ruined and destroyed? It is an unconscious drive we will talk about it with depression.

Generalized anxiety disorder

The essential feature of this disorder is generalized and persistent anxiety, which is not limited and does not even predominate in any particular environmental circumstance (ie, it is a "floating free anguish"). As in the case of other anxiety disorders, the predominant symptoms are very variable, but the most frequent ones are complaints of constant nervousness, tremors, muscular tension, sweating, dizziness, palpitations, dizziness and epigastric discomfort. Fears are often expressed that one or a family member will fall ill or have an accident,

along with other concerns and very different feelings. This disorder is more common in women and is often associated with chronic environmental stress. Its course is variable, but tends to be fluctuating and chronic.

Guidelines for diagnosis

The affected person should have anxiety symptoms most days for at least several weeks in a row. Among them must be present features of:

- A) Apprehension (worries about coming calamities, feeling “on the edge”, difficulties of concentration, etc.).
- B) Muscle tension (psychomotor agitation and restlessness, tension headaches, tremors, inability to relax).
- C) Vegetative hyperactivity (dizziness, sweating, tachycardia or tachypnea, epigastric discomfort, vertigo, dry mouth, etc.).

The constant need for security and recurring somatic complaints are often striking.

Psychodynamic understanding of ruin, bankruptcy, destruction of wealth, money and capital, suicide

In normal conditions the psychic apparatus tries to generate wealth, money and capital to be able to buy sex. However, in some pathological circumstances the psychic apparatus assaults itself by generating poverty, misery, ruin, destruction of wealth, money, capital, goods and services.

The causes of this autoaggression are diverse, depression, reduction of neurotransmitters such as serotonin in the central nervous system, genetic factors, environmental, etc. Regardless of the cause, tanatic psychodynamic impulses can generate aggression to investors (heteroagresiones) or self-aggressions, realizing harmful economic and financial practices that instead of generating wealth, money, capital, it does destroy everything.

Economic and financial self-harm satisfies guilty fantasies, makes improper financial transactions to lose money and thereby self-punishes, thus hurting investors alike. Or hatred displaces anger and resentment toward him or someone else, generating economic losses to discharge his tanatic drive.

Another aspect of economic and financial losses is due to inadequate scams or management by investors or financial advisors, not because of the heteroaggressive or self-aggressive tanatic drive, but rather as a control disorder of the impulses that gives rise to excesses in the proper behavior of financial advisors or investors by impulsiveness.

Major Depressive Disorder. Diagnostic Criteria DSM-V (American Psychiatric Association) [4] Major Depressive Disorder (DSM-5)

Five (or more) of the following symptoms have been present during the same 2-week period, which represent a change from the previous one; at least one of the symptoms should be (1) depressed mood or (2) loss of interest or pleasure.

1. Depressive mood most of the day, almost every day as indicated by the subject (for example, feels sad, empty, without hope) or the observation made by others (for example, it seems tearful). (Note: In children and adolescents, mood can be irritable.)
2. Marked decrease in interest or pleasure in all or almost all activities, most of the day, almost every day (according to the subject or observe).
3. significant weight loss without dieting or weight gain (eg a change of more than 5% of body weight in a month), or decreased or increased appetite almost every day. (Note: In children, the failure to make the expected weight gain must be assessed).
4. Insomnia or hypersomnia almost every day.
5. Psychomotor agitation or slowing almost every day (observable by others, not just feelings of restlessness or being slowed down).
6. Fatigue or loss of energy almost every day.
7. Excessive or inappropriate feelings of worthlessness or guilt (which can be delusional) almost every day (not just remorse or guilt about being ill).
8. Decreased ability to think or concentrate, or indecision, almost every day (either a subjective attribution or an observation from others).
9. Recurrent thoughts of death (not just fear of death), recurrent suicidal ideation without a specific plan or suicide attempt, or a specific suicide plan.

B. Symptoms cause clinically significant discomfort or impairment in social, occupational, or other important areas of functioning.

Economic formula of the psychic apparatus

Economy = sex + food to survive: Sex is the fundamental reason of the psychic apparatus, the preservation of the species and the genetic legacy, is the most important, it is the only thing that matters.

In some circumstances sex prevails and is more important than food and self preservation, men prefer to lose their lives by discharging the sexual drive.

Price of Sex in men = (quality x quantity) ∞: The amount of sex for men is unlimited, the psychic apparatus wants to have as many sexual relations as possible in an infinite way. The quality of sex for men is unlimited, the psychic apparatus wants to have sex with the most physically attractive person, which is synonymous with health.

Price of Sex in women = quantity + (quality) ∞ + money

Price of Love in women = good genes (money * physical attractiveness * intelligence)

Price of Love in men = good genes (physical attraction ∞) + (money + intelligence)

The amount of sex for women is limited, the psychic apparatus wants to have sex once every 9 months during the reproductive stage. The quality of sex for women is unlimited, the psychic apparatus wants to have sex with the most physically attractive person, which is synonymous with health. Women add money to the equation since it offers benefits for the survival of offspring.

Economy = price of sex = price of love = infinite ∞ : The economy is equal to the price of sex, and the price of sex is equal to the price of love, and the price of love is equal to infinity, so the psychic apparatus is never satisfied, it is always unhappy and unsatisfied, is satisfied totally and partially only temporarily.

Analogy between the analysis of investments in portfolios of investment values or portfolios and the mathematical formula of sex, love, economy and happiness.

In the principles of Investment in financial instruments there is a maxim that says: "Investors deserve the rewards they get in the financial markets as compensation for the service to take the risk". In financial terms, a portfolio of securities or investment portfolios is a collection of securities held by a single investor and the main objective of forming a portfolio is to diversify risk, allocate the necessary energy to different values to reduce the risk of economic loss and maximize profits.

The main analogies for measuring happiness through portfolio theory relate first to the fact that just as in the securities portfolios the expected gain is measured in terms of the amount of money allocated to each financial instrument by the profitability of this instrument, we can indicate that happiness is a function of the energy assigned to each one of the variables that produces it for the profitability offered by each of them, always assuming that for each person the happiness factors may be different from those of another person, that is, some people prefer to sleep rather than eat, others prefer having sex rather than eating, while others feel more satisfaction producing money than any of the other variables in their environment.

Second, it is assumed that each person has information about the values of each variable that affect them or produce personal satisfaction, and finally it is assumed that each person will only be interested in the expected result depending on the energy destined for each value and risk they assume each time they try to increase that value.

Unlike the capital markets in which the information to be analyzed depends on factors that are not controlled by the investors, in the case of happiness through the formula of the economy, sex, love and happiness is maximized depending on the efforts made in the values chosen as main.

In a hypothetical example in which a person establishes that the most important values to obtain personal happiness are SEX and MONEY then the expected result will be:

$$F(E): W_a \times (E_{s_a}) + W_b \times (E_{s_b})$$

Where:

F(E) = Expected Happiness

W_a = weight or importance assigned to value A (SEX)

E_{s_a} = Effort applied to obtain the maximum yield of value A (SEX)

W_b = Weight or importance assigned to value B (MONEY)

E_{s_b} = Effort applied to obtain the maximum yield of value B (MONEY)

In this case the sum of $W_a + W_b = 100\%$ of personal satisfaction

And so too, $E_{s_a} + E_{s_b} = 100\%$ of the personal effort, knowing that we can not allocate all our effort in these two values only since we have to eat, sleep, work, study, etc.

The fundamental decision is then to determine which values will give us the greatest happiness and how much effort we will dedicate to satisfy them, taking as a parameter that a 50% positive final result to measure our happiness will also be 50% unhappiness, The result of applying the equation must always be greater than 50%.

Then as an example, if we assign a 40% weight or importance to SEX and we apply a 30% effort while we assign 60% to produce MONEY to which we apply a 20% effort, our parameter of personal satisfaction or "Happiness " be:

$$F(E) = 0,4 \times 0,3 + 0,6 \times 0,2 = 0,24 \text{ or } 24\% \text{ of personal satisfaction}$$

Although it was said that it should be greater than 50%, it is important to emphasize that not included in the equation are all the activities that develop in a day of work and that can produce satisfaction or happiness (sleep, eat, work), so To have included only 50% of effort (30% of the SEX and 20% of the MONEY) to obtain a 24% of 50% results in 48% of satisfaction, which brings us closer to the ideal of it.

In this analysis it is determined that one of the values prevails over the other if it occurs that offers expected satisfaction greater than the other with a smaller or the same effort to achieve it, and that is where the user's attention must be concentrated on the values which represent less effort and greater satisfaction.

On the other hand there is a remnant energy, not used productively and that does not produce satisfaction or happiness and has to do with non-effective leisure times that occur when we drive, or queue at banks or in an office to process a request, for what pretending to demand 100% effort in a normal day means to use the 24 hours in productive activities to obtain happiness and that is impossible.

As a referential average it can be established that a person "loses" one third of the day in non-productive activities and

if on average he sleeps 8 hours a day (although sleep would be included in the values of pleasure and happiness), any human being can dedicate no more of one-third of your normal day to apply the efforts necessary for personal satisfaction or happiness.

Risk in a «Two Assets Portfolio»

If we take as valid the postulates to measure the expected happiness with the weighted average of the importance of each of the values that we care to achieve it by the effort applied to obtain it, we must use the analogy of risk analysis in investment portfolios for measure the risk of applying our efforts to obtain them, measuring the results obtained in each period of application.

Thus in Investment Analysis it is said that “the risk of a portfolio depends on the risk of each of the securities in the portfolio, the percentage of funds invested in each and the tendency they have to covariate the yields of the securities. Wallet in time”

By similarity then “the risk of obtaining happiness will depend on the risk that we run with each value that produces it, the percentage of effort that we apply to obtain it and the yields produced by each value selected in the periods of application”

It is understood that risk measurement is not timely, at a time for an instantaneous result but rather a systematic measurement from period to period of application of the effort, calculating the trends of the results, as if it were the analysis of variation of the actions in the stock exchange and pondering the results obtained in each value, so, if we dedicate an effort to obtain money and we achieve the goal we can associate this achievement with the performance of this value, and also if we dedicate effort to achieve sex we should try to ponder in what measure was achieved, so we can know where we should devote more effort to achieve our personal satisfaction and therefore greater happiness mathematically speaking and in measuring risk we will know if we should devote more effort to a value over others or if we simply need to change the weights of each of them to obtain a result of personal satisfaction more adapted to our needs and expectations.

Example of application of risk measurement

In order to explain in detail how the risk of our so-called “Happiness Portfolio” would be measured, we will use an example based on the Sex and Money Values with the weights assigned above and the effort to achieve them.

Since the risk of a portfolio depends on the risk of each of its values and the happiness (yield) they produce, one can mathematically measure the tendency of the results to move together through the covariance of the results of the values.

To estimate the value of the risk, we assume that the following values of happiness were obtained in a study period (again not including all aspects, only two: sex and money).

PERIOD	VALUE A: SEX			VALUE A: MONEY		
	PERFORMANCE	MEDIA	DEVIATION	PERFORMANCE	MEDIA	DEVIATION
1	0,18	0,078	0,102	0,14	0,06	0,082
2	0,15	0,078	0,072	0,09	0,06	0,032
3	-0,13	0,078	-0,208	0,02	0,06	-0,038
4	0,05	0,078	-0,028	-0,03	0,06	-0,088
5	0,14	0,078	0,062	0,07	0,06	0,012
6	0,078	0,078	0,000	0,06	0,06	0,000

Taking the individual Performance (Happiness) in each study period, the average of the same is calculated as

$$\text{Media A} = (0,18+0,15-0,13+0,05+0,14) / 5 = 0,078$$

$$\text{Media B} = (0,14+0,09++0,02-0,03+0,07) / 5 = 0,06$$

And the individual deviation:

$$\text{Deviation} = \text{Average} - \text{Yield}$$

If the calculation is correct the sum of the deviations for each value must be zero.

For each period we multiply the value of the respective deviation of each value by the deviation of the other and obtain the sum of all the products (Table 2).

PERIOD	VALUE A: SEX		VALUE A: MONEY		RESULTS
	DEVIATION		DEVIATION		
	0,102	X	0,082	=	0,00836
	0,072	X	0,032	=	0,00230
	-0,208	X	-0,032	=	0,00790
	-0,028	X	-0,088	=	0,00246
	0,062	X	0,012	=	0,00074
				SUMMARY	0,02178

We then calculate the covariance of the values, dividing this sum by the number of periods analyzed

$$\text{COV a, b} = (0,02178) / 5 = 0,0044$$

Then the Variance of the two Values will be:

$$\text{VAR(E)} = \text{Wa}^2 \times \text{VARa} + \text{Wb}^2 \times \text{VARb} + 2\text{Wa} \times \text{Wb} \times \text{COVa,b}$$

Where:

VAR (E) = Variance of the expected value of happiness according to these two Assets

Wa = weight assigned to value A (Sex)

Wb = weight assigned to value B (Money)

VARa = variance of Value A for the study period of 5 months

VARb = Value B variance for the study period of 5 months

COVa, b = the covariance between the two Securities or assets.

We determine the Variance and Standard Deviation of each of the values that are but a measure of dispersion of the results

that indicate if the values that we obtain by period are more or less adjusted, that is to say if we maintain a uniformity in our results, And if they give very high means that we get good results and bad results but we are not uniform in them.

PERIOD	VALUE A: SEX			VALUE A: MONEY		
	PERFORMANCE	$X_i - \text{MEDIA}$	$(X_i - \text{MEDIA})^2$	PERFORMANCE	$X_i - \text{MEDIA}$	$(X_i - \text{MEDIA})^2$
1	0,18	0,10	0,01040	0,14	0,08	0,00672
2	0,15	0,07	0,00518	0,09	0,03	0,00102
3	-0,13	-0,21	0,04326	0,02	-0,04	0,00144
4	0,05	-0,03	0,00078	-0,03	-0,09	0,00774
5	0,14	0,06	0,00384	0,07	0,00	0,00014
MEDIA	0,078	SUMA	0,063	0,058	N-1	0,017
		N - 1	4,000		VARINACE	4,000
		VARINACE	0,0159		DESV. EST.	0,0043
		DESV. EST.	0,1260			0,0653

If at VALUE A (SEX) we had assigned an importance of 40% and an effort to obtain it of 30% and VALUE B (MONEY) an importance of 60% with an effort of 20% we can already calculate the variance of our "Portfolios Of Happiness "for this period of study

$$\text{VAR}(E) = (0,4 \times 0,4 \times 0,0159) + (0,6 \times 0,6 \times 0,0043) + 2 (0,4 * 0,6 * 0,0044) = 0,0062$$

And the standard deviation of the "Happiness" Variable will be the square root of the portfolio variance

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \text{VAR}(E)^{1/2} = 0,0788$$

The standard deviation of the Portfolio as a measure of dispersion is indicative of how the individual values may differ from the mean of the data and has the same units of the variable under study so it is measured in "Happiness" that we calculated before in 24% and now with a low deviation of just 7.8% which indicates that our efforts to obtain sex and money are consistent with results with very little dispersion.

Finally, in the risk weighting of our "Happiness Portfolio" we must determine the value of the correlation that is a measure of how the values assigned to the portfolio are "moved" in relation to one another, that is, if one rises to what extent the other will rise and vice versa, so the correlation between two assets will always be between minus -1 and 1.

If the correlation is greater than zero, this means that the two assets or values tend to move in the same direction and the effort invested in both will be reflected in success by the pursuit of Happiness, whereas if it is less than zero implies that The two variables move in opposite directions and mean that when we get a positive value in one of them it is because in the other we are losing value and we must rethink the strategy. If the correlation between the two variables is zero, then there is no relationship between them and the efforts and their results are independent of each other, so if we maybe get happiness in Sex we are getting lost in Money and the final evaluation would be Negative for our happiness.

For the example developed so far, the calculation of the Correlation Coefficient will be:

$$\text{Correlation } a, b = (\text{VOC } a, b) / (\text{Standard Deviation A } \times \text{Standard Deviation B})$$

$$\text{Correlation } a, b = 0,0044 / (0,1260 \times 0,0653) = 0,53$$

In this case the correlation coefficient indicates not only that we are obtaining good results in our search for happiness, but that both values selected are strongly related to each other, so that both are being effective for the final result.

Hence, the objective of measuring the HAPPINESS obtained with these equations leads us to determine how correlated are the values chosen as important for our search and, if the results were negative, to where we should direct our efforts to improve them.

Properties of the mathematical formula of SEX, Love, ECONOMY and happiness.

It is obvious that the application of the developed formula needs guidance parameters to be able to follow and to use it since the mathematical values applied on quantitative variables is not an easy task, so the following suggestions are given:

- 1.- Given the above in relation to the effective daily time, it is not recommended to allocate more than 50% of daily effort to the sum of the selected values.
2. As there are many activities that can lead to a supposed Happiness such as work, sleep, sex, money or eating should not all be included in the analysis since equations with more than two Assets or Values become unmanageable.

We recommend using the postulates developed by Wilfredo Pareto at the beginning of the 20th century, which establish that 80% of our problems come from 20% of the causes, that is to say that if we concentrate on two possible VALUES maybe when solving them and weighting them we will notice that 80% of our activities also improve.

This postulate is known as the Rule of the 80/20 and is used in quality control as a technique to separate the "few Vitals" from the "many Trivials" because it allows identifying the most important problems to dedicate time and effort and not lose both In trivial problems.

- 3.- Having internalized the fact that MONEY and SEX are probably the two vital values (20), it is necessary to determine a methodology to measure the level of expected performance and to assess if it has been obtained.

It could be said for SEX that a function of periodicity is established at least once a day, in the most optimal case, or the week or as it is always provided that at the end of the study period is established percentage if it was achieved the objective

Thus, if it is decided that it should be 3 times a week and

only obtained twice, the expected performance in the period will be $2/3$ or 66%.

Similarly with MONEY, if we expect to obtain an amount over the same period, we can determine what percentage of success we have calculated based on the expected value.

Both percentage calculations are set as the E_s and E_b values of the initial equation.

Now we must assign a weight of importance to each of the chosen VALUES, that is, SEX and MONEY, as a measure of which of the two would give us greater happiness in obtaining them, (if it is the same then it would be 50% each).

This percentage weight would enter into the initial equation as W_a and W_b .

Finally, the evaluation period should be established based on the availability of going out in search of HAPPINESS.

Psychodynamic analysis of religion in the economy, capital markets and financial markets

Religion determines through the superego, the structure of the psychic apparatus that represses the discharges of the sexual drives of the id, that superego that is determined by ethical and moral norms of the society, religion structures the superego, reason why religions like Buddhist, or some Hinduism where they promote asceticism, renunciation of desire to achieve happiness, renunciation of desire is not really happiness, but renouncing desire diminishes pain and suffering through psychodynamic defense mechanisms such as dissociation or repression. To renounce the desire and to give up the basic psychodynamic impulses of the unconscious means to renounce sex, to renounce sex means to renounce the generation of wealth, capital, money, to be able to buy sex. This implies a decrease in productivity, a decrease in wealth, a decrease in capital, a decrease in money, poverty, misery.

Another consideration is that suppressing or dissociating the drive decreases pain and suffering but with a very great emotional and emotional cost, the natural and normal for the psychic apparatus is to unload unconscious psychodynamic sexual drives, trying to repress them generates a huge conflict, for what the religions that try to go against the normal functioning of the psychic apparatus like Hinduism Buddhism, Catholicism, Protestantism, Islam, etc. are not viable in the long run and doomed to failure.

Religions such as the Catholic have dogmas where it is bad and negative to be rich, "it is easier for a camel to go through the eye of a needle than a rich man enters the kingdom of the heavens" this explains to a great extent the poor economic performance of the nations Catholics compared to Protestants where dogma is the generation of wealth to enter the kingdom of the heavens.

Psychodynamic analysis of political systems in the economy, capital markets and financial markets

Political systems determine through the superego, the structure of the psychic apparatus that represses the discharges

of the sexual drives of the id, that superego that is determined by ethical and moral norms of the society, the political system structures the superego, reason why systems politicians such as socialism or communism, where they promote asceticism, renunciation of desire to achieve happiness, renunciation of desire is not really happiness, but renouncing desire diminishes pain and suffering through psychodynamic defense mechanisms such as dissociation or repression. To renounce the desire and to give up the basic psychodynamic impulses of the unconscious means to renounce sex, to renounce sex means to renounce the generation of wealth, capital, money, to be able to buy sex. This implies a decrease in productivity, a decrease in wealth, a decrease in capital, a decrease in money, poverty, misery.

Another consideration is that suppressing or dissociating the drive decreases pain and suffering but with a very great emotional and emotional cost, the natural and normal for the psychic apparatus is to unload unconscious psychodynamic sexual drives, trying to repress them generates a huge conflict, doctrines that try to run counter to the normal functioning of the psychic apparatus like socialism and communism are not viable in the long run and are doomed to failure.

Another important aspect to consider is that socialist and communist systems promote common goods, reject and deny material possessions and capital accumulation, this is completely antagonistic to the normal functioning of the psychic apparatus, which establishes an individuation between one subject and another, as normal development, common goods implies a fusion of the psychic apparatus, this fusion of the psychic apparatus implies a psychosis which is a pathological state of the psychic apparatus, the normal must be the individualization between subjects, so that own wealth, own capital, money, individual, accumulation of wealth, capital, goods and services is a normal and healthy development of the psychic apparatus in the individual, so that capitalist economic system is the one that can really be imposed and prevail in society, given that is consistent with the normal functioning of the psyche. The redistribution of wealth is unnatural, the psychic apparatus tends to accumulate wealth, money, capital infinitely, trying to avoid the redistribution of wealth.

Capitalist political systems have dogmas where it is good and positive to be rich, this largely accounts for the better economic performance of capitalist nations compared to socialist or communist ones. The natural and normal for the psychic apparatus is to unload unconscious sexual psychodynamic drives, so that the doctrines that promote the normal functioning of the psychic apparatus such as capitalism are viable in the long run and doomed to success.

In capitalism, narcissistic psychic structures (those that only care about personal satisfaction, individual) are those that best represent it, but this narcissism is positive in capitalist statements, and establish that self-benefit ends up favoring the collective benefit of society, however that narcissism has to be socialized since if psychopathic narcissistic drives are discharged then instead of ending up benefiting society, it ends

up hurting it. Anarchy is the typical example of a psychopathic political system, while capitalism with a minimal state (courts, judges, prosecutors, police systems) is the typical case of socialized narcissism, which is the only viable for the psychic apparatus. Socialism or communism would be psychosis, completely unfeasible in the long run.

The psychic apparatus is monopolistic wants to monopolize, dominate and control if it is in its possibilities, if it is to eliminate the monopoly would generate problems in the system. Exploitation is natural in the psychic apparatus, everyone wants to exploit others, unless they have masochistic drives (we do not know their prevalence), except that society regulates exploitation for cost-benefit. The exploitation of man by man or by a system is not exploitation, it is a simple exchange of goods just like others.

Psychodynamic analysis of offer and demand

The demand is infinite since the man wants to have sexual intercourse every day several times a day with the greatest number of women, the most possible and the best quality possible, that is to say the most attractive physically, which is the synonym of health. The offer is very limited and scarce, since women want to have sex only 1 every 9 months during their reproductive period, so the frequency is much lower than in men. They need a single man who fecundates them, so they need fewer men. They want the highest possible quality, that is the most attractive possible. Equally it incorporates man's wealth into the equation since money offers security in our society. So the demands of the woman are difficult to satisfy just like the man. This limited offer of sex by women and the infinite demand for sex by men increases the costs of sex exponentially, so that man is forced to generate wealth, money and capital infinitely to satisfy infinitely his desire to discharge the sexual drive to reduce suffering and increase happiness.

Women demand wealth, money and capital in an infinite way to try to satisfy their original lack and their infinite basic psychodynamic desires and impulses, which are never satisfied, nor are they ever filled. As they want sex with such a low frequency the rest of the time they try to satisfy themselves with goods and services that cost money.

Psychodynamic understanding of trust and investor mistrust

As socialized beings, human beings have, in normal conditions, a biological and psychic predisposition to trust other people, even though the unconscious discharges narcissistic psychodynamic drives to satisfy themselves, those narcissistic drives that seek the individual's own individual benefit, ends up as John Smith posited in capitalism benefiting society in general, hence our psychic apparatus is trusted and extremely vulnerable to financial advisers, scammers, predators, psychopaths, and so on. That is why all those involved in the economic and financial system must be very cautious and paranoid and thus reduce the risks generated by the natural confidence of individuals in society.

Psychodynamic understanding of financial advisers and narcissistic and psychopathic investors

Psychopathic: The psychopathic or socioeconomic psychic structures are extremely dangerous, they can generate wealth, money and capital for taking risky and reckless actions, however this economic behavior is unethical, immoral, which can bring problems to the economic system in general, violating the reliability of investors. There is also the risk of scams by these structures. Antisocial personality disorder (TPA), sometimes called sociopath or psychopathy, is a pathology of a psychic nature, people who suffer from it lose the notion of the importance of social norms, such as individual laws and rights. Although it can be detected from 18 years of age, it is estimated that the symptoms and characteristics have been developing since adolescence. Before the age of 15, a similar but not so marked symptomatology must be detected.

Criteria for the diagnosis of F60.2 antisocial personality disorder

A. A general pattern of contempt and violation of the rights of others that is presented from the age of 15, as indicated by three (or more) of the following items:

1. Failure to adapt to social norms in terms of legal behavior, as indicated by repeatedly perpetrating acts that are grounds for arrest
2. Dishonesty, indicated by lying repeatedly, using an alias, defrauding others for personal gain or pleasure
3. Impulsivity or inability to plan the future
4. Irritability and aggressiveness, indicated by repeated physical fights or aggressions
5. Unconcerned unconcerned about your safety or that of others
6. Persistent irresponsibility, indicated by the inability to keep a job with constancy or to take charge of economic obligations
7. Lack of remorse, as indicated by the indifference or justification of having damaged, mistreated or robbed others.

Narcissistic; Narcissistic structures are economically productive and behave similar to psychopathic structures. However, they are a bit more functional and tend to commit fewer crimes and financial crimes than psychopaths. Narcissism is important for a financial advisor and an investor, since the ideological and philosophical conceptualization of capitalism is the pursuit of self-profit. This individual and individual benefit, if properly channeled, brings benefits to society in general.

Diagnosis according to DSM IV

A general pattern of grandiosity (in imagination or behavior), a need for admiration and a lack of empathy, beginning at the

beginning of adulthood and occurring in different contexts as indicated by five (or more) of the Following items: 1

He has a great sense of self-importance (eg, he exaggerates achievements and abilities, expects to be recognized as superior, without proportionate achievements).

He is preoccupied with fantasies of unlimited success, power, brilliance, beauty or imaginary love.

It believes that it is “special” and unique and that it can only be understood by or can only be related to other people (or institutions) that are special or high status.

It demands excessive admiration.

It is very pretentious, for example, unreasonable expectations of receiving a special favor treatment or that their expectations are automatically met.

He is interpersonally exploitative, for example, takes advantage of others to achieve his own goals.

It lacks empathy: it is reluctant to recognize or identify with the feelings and needs of others.

He often envies others or believes others envy him.

Has arrogant or arrogant behavior or attitude.

Psychodynamic understanding of game theory

The game of the dike: The Nash equation and game theory, which is generally used in economics to predict better outcomes, presupposes that the players’ psychic apparatus is logical and rational, which is completely false, the psychic apparatus is neither logical nor rational. It assumes that if players do not play in a certain logical way, such as personal or mutual benefit, the action is a silly response. But as economists and finance people can explain suicide in a financial assistant or investor. It is explained by understanding that the psychic apparatus discharges drives to satisfy themselves that they are not necessarily the best for the individual or society [5].

In the psychodynamic understanding of the game of the dam for example Adan does not care that the water will destroy his house, he is only interested in downloading his sexual instincts with Eva, only if he saves his house will have greater statistical possibility that he can download his drives with Eva, Since Eva needs a house, so that her offspring are more likely to survive. If water destroys Eva’s house, Adan will not be interested in anything, on the contrary, it may benefit him because Eva is more vulnerable to have more possibility to discharge his sexual drives with her. In most cases, in cases where so-called foolish responses occur, Adan is at risk of losing his home by saving Eve, or even destroying the two houses, the problem with these silly answers is that we do not know which drive has the psychic apparatus and can download any.

Benefits of anxiety in the economy and financial markets

Anxiety in men occurs as a mechanism of alert or defense against imminent danger, in this case the most important

imminent danger for the man is not having sex, he does not have sex because he does not have the money to buy it, so anxiety is generated by not having money to buy sex, this generates that the central nervous system generates volitions, drives, wills, attitudes for work, production, generation of wealth, capital, money, for this reason anxiety is positive to generate wealth. The lack of anxiety would generate the opposite in men, if we did not have anxiety, because sex quality and quantity would be very economic and abundant, then we had no need to work and generate money, wealth or capital, Buddhists are abstemious, to desires, such as money and sex, so that as they dissociate their drives, their desires, diminishes their pain and suffering. But they have low economic productivity, little money and little capital, so that anxiety is directly proportional to the generation of wealth. An excess of anxiety is pathological and the subject can not function properly in society to generate wealth, money and capital, so that the management of society must be balanced.

Anxiety management therapy

Psychoeducation: educating the general population on economic issues is fundamental for the proper management of anxiety, with the knowledge of economics individuals will be less likely to react in the financial markets in such a volatile, fluctuating and erratic way. Investors would not make purchases or sales eager for psychic conditions that have nothing to do with real economic factors. Even a group of approximately 20% of investors with tanatic psychodynamic drives would be vulnerable, however, psychoeducation in financial matters would reduce their symptoms and, therefore, inappropriate and counterproductive reactions.

There are negative aspects regarding the financial psychoeducation, some operations in the markets are carried out in an inadequate, antithetical, immoral, risky way, reason why an important component of the stock systems and banks, operate based on these psychopathic behaviors on the part of the operators, with economic psychoeducation in the population, investors would take more precautions and an important part of the irresponsible financial system would disappear. However this would be better for him, system in general, since it would reduce risky decisions and with it volatility, destruction and loss of wealth.

Pharmacotherapy: Medications are not suitable for managing anxiety in the capital markets and economy since it would have to medicate all individuals and this is not feasible. Therefore, the medication would only be indicated to individuals with clinical disorders of anxiety or other psychiatric disorders [6-10].

Gene therapy: So far we lack the technology and knowledge for gene therapies that reduce anxiety but at the same time increase volition for work, wealth generation, productivity, money, capital. Although research in the future should be geared to solving this problem.

Cardiovascular Exercises: People should do 45 minutes to 1 hour of cardiovascular exercise 7 days a week, it can be in the mornings, afternoons or evenings, at any time.

Why are cardiovascular exercises important? There are multiple reasons, first of all they are very healthy from the medical, health point of view for the body, but besides this they are very favorable for mental health, they increase your cognitive capacities enormously (healthy mind in healthy body), but it Most important of all, are very favorable to the emotional health of people, as well as during cardiovascular exercise they release a lot of mediators and substances in the body beneficial to the body and mind, likewise releases catecholamines and other neurotransmitters Which generate incredible emotional health: serotonin, noradrenaline, dopamine, endorphins, endocannabinoids, adrenaline, oxytocin, among many others. These substances produce a feeling of emotional well-being in people, which decreases depression, pain, suffering, anxiety and prepares you to deal with problems of couple more easily.

The other positive factor of cardiovascular exercises is that it improves your physical appearance, one of the most important factors if you know how to channel for happiness in relationships. Physically attractive people are more capable of being more tolerant of their partners, and allow attractive people to download violent, aggressive drives with greater tolerance to deal with their partner's problems.

Physically unattractive people have much more difficulty in making their partners tolerant to them and thus the suffering in relationships may be greater. This is not to say that attractive people are totally happy, quite the opposite, attractive people also have a lot of suffering, what I want to say is that attractive tax is an important tool if you know how to use it properly.

Any place work, the important thing is that you realize them. Outdoors is free, and very pleasant, the drawback is that you have no social link there, so social linking can be done in other scenarios. In a gym it is expensive you are locked up but the positive aspect is that there is social bonding. At home is the least recommended, there is no enjoyment of the environment or social connection with other people, but if it is the only option you have, then it is okay, what is important is that you do cardiovascular exercises daily.

Some of the disadvantages of doing cardiovascular exercises is that you have to invest a lot of time every day of your life in them, and for a society as complex as this, where you have to invest a lot of energy in studies, work, family, etc. The practice of daily cardiovascular exercises seems practically impossible to perform. Now if it is true that you believe that you should invest energy in other activities the key to happiness is to prioritize fundamental activities. Daily cardiovascular exercise is more important than studies, work and family, it is preferable to leave the studies, work and family and dedicate your time as a priority to daily cardiovascular exercises. At this point you must be arguing, but how? The writer must be crazy, how will I leave my studies, my work and my family for the exercises? Well, you are not really going to leave them, just that you are going to prioritize the exercises on all of them. Later explain what are the psychodynamic mechanisms unconscious for happiness, and happiness as a couple has nothing to do with work or studies or family.

Spiritual bonding: people must do some spiritual and religious ritual at least once a week, any religion is good, Catholic, Christian, Jewish, Muslim, Buddhist, Hindu, etc. Spirituality is one of the main centers of human restraint. They have an ideological and philosophical conception that gives meaning to life, that decreases anxiety especially if the person presents a weak psychic apparatus. In the same way during the practice of religious rituals you have social connection with other people, this is very positive.

One of the negative elements of religions is that they represent just one of the components of the Supermicro structures of the psychic apparatus, that structure that is responsible for repressing and frustrating the erotic impulses of the It, which produces suffering, pain, anxiety, the Depression. So it is important that spiritual bonding alone take the positive aspects of religion and discard and discard the negative aspects. What are the negative aspects of religion? Everything that represses the discharge of the erotic drive, which represses genitalization, sex, promiscuity, polygamy, orgies, which is what generates happiness in people and success in relationships.

So you can practice spiritual bonding but you must be aware that no matter what religious leaders say, you must be very convinced that you have to practice downloading the erotic drive, genitalization, sex, promiscuity, Polygamy, orgies, which is what generates happiness in people and success in relationships.

For people who are atheists and do not believe in religions, it is important that they at least have philosophical or practice meditation, new age and these energetic spiritual practices that are well tolerated for atheists.

Work relationships: all people who want to be happy, have to be financially autonomous, have to be able to self-finance.

"If a woman depends economically on a man, she will be absolutely and completely unhappy, she will have depression, suffering, pain, anxiety, and this will be consciously or unconsciously".

The economic independence of women is one of the main keys to the happiness of women. This is not to say that economically independent women are totally happy, quite the opposite, financially autonomous women can suffer greatly, what we mean is that if used properly it is an important tool as well as the physical attractiveness to achieve happiness.

How much should a woman earn financially to be happy? Only the minimum necessary to satisfy your basic requirements of food, shelter and health. Anything additional to basic requirements helps increase people's quality of life, but they are not essential. So women should prioritize physical exercise and physical attractiveness over all other things.

How much should a woman study to be happy? The minimum necessary to obtain a job that meets your basic requirements. If you have a doctorate in nuclear physics at Harvard, you are fine, the higher your academic degree, the more you will be

able to sublimate libidinal charge and enjoy life, but it is not the priority for happiness, it is just a complement and should not be prioritized over physical attractiveness.

How much money should a man earn to be happy? The answer is complex, but the pragmatic answer is: all the money you can. The more money a man has, the more chance he has of being happy, happiness in man is determined by the discharge of the sexual drive, if he can have sex with couples as often as possible there lies his happiness. And money is perhaps the most powerful tool today for a man to discharge his sexual instincts and have sex and above all quality sex (with attractive women and good sexual performance).

In reality money does not give happiness to man, happiness lies in sex, but in the society in which we live, money can buy sex, so it is the necessary element for the happiness of man.

Now men who want to be happy must comply with these guidelines:

1) Do not ever marry their partners, marriage does not ensure sex in relationships, so it does not guarantee your happiness. Also, from the financial point of view it is much cheaper to have sex with prostitutes than the money you have to invest with your partner and your family. Multiple studies confirm the economic benefits of having sex with prostitutes compared to formal wives or partners. Similarly, having sex with prostitutes guarantees diversity, something you do not get with a formal couple, where you should always have sex with the same couple, something very boring for men. Having sex with prostitutes guarantees sexual satisfaction, since they are professionals for these purposes.

Also having sex with prostitutes saves all the effort you have to do with seduction among other social protocols. In addition, having sex with prostitutes avoids having to tolerate the discharges of the violent and aggressive drives of women which generates suffering in man.

The negative aspects of prostitutes are that they are relatively expensive (always cheaper than couples and wives) but the resource is not free, so the man can not access it whenever he wants, so it can not be happy every time you want. The fact that a man has to pay money to be happy generates a huge violence in his psychic apparatus, either consciously or unconsciously. Women to be happy should be physically attractive, while physical attractiveness is a genetic predisposition, they can do a lot from the environmental point of view to improve their physical appearance. But in addition to being physically attractive, women must sexually satisfy their partners as long as their partner requires it, and most important of all, without sex implying an energy expenditure for the man, that is, that he does not have to consume energy in seduction, dinners, outings, discos, movies, you do not have to spend any money either. If the man has to spend energy in seduction, that generates a huge violence in his unconscious and his psychic apparatus, probably consciously the man is comfortable spending all that energy to get sex, but unconsciously the violence that will generate will be huge.

The violence that man can generate innocently can manifest itself with: infidelity, physical abuse, psychological mistreatment, verbal abuse, abandonment, apathy in the relationship, among many other symptoms.

Women will wonder: Why my partner is unfaithful, because he mistreats me psychologically, because he mistreats me physically, because he mistreats me verbally, because I abandon myself? The answer is very simple, because they had to spend energy to get sex. It is important to understand that because these are unconscious psychodynamic mechanisms, man does not know why he brutally attacks his partners, he only does it unconsciously, although consciously, he believes that he does not want to do so. He thinks he feels uncomfortable and unsatisfied in the relationship.

The other important aspect is that the tanatic (death) drive, which is a violent and aggressive drive present in men and that generates all the violence towards their partners, is a residual drive, stored, accumulated throughout their life in the apparatus psychic. Violence in men accumulated from about 15 to 35 years, when they have to spend more energy to get sex. From the age of 35 to 45 the energy expenditure for having sex is lower, which leads to less violence towards couples, but this also explains why men in these ages are more difficult to master.

But if the man has a stable partner of 35 to 45 years may want to separate, or resort to infidelity, if he will be financially hurt during the divorce.

That is why it is fundamental that men never marry, since they will be economically vulnerable during couple problems and divorce. While if they are not married, they will have more economic solvency capacity to buy sex with prostitutes and be happy. The problem with not marrying is that women are very pressured by this, of course, they are looking for their economic stability with the least possible effort, to be able to guarantee their descendants a greater possibility of subsistence. However, the key in men is not to give in to pressure, blackmail, or manipulation, you must strengthen your psychic apparatus and understand that it is always cheaper to buy sex from a prostitute than to have to finance a stable partner economically. In addition to the benefits of the diversity of many women and the benefits of sexual satisfaction for having relationships with a professional in the field. In addition, you should not spend energy in seduction something that is extremely humiliating for men. Nor do you have to tolerate the violent and aggressive impulses of a stable couple, which are very frequent, the women discharge all the violence towards the object relation that they have nearer, that usually is their pair.

If the man has to marry because it is extremely necessary, he will have to do it with capitulations, and these must be closed, so that everything that you have before the marriage and during the marriage, exclusively of him at the time of the divorce, is It is important to bear in mind that children have important roles from a financial and legal point of view, so it is a priority that they also do not have children, which generates economic vulnerability during the couple's problems.

If a man wants to have children, he must do so after he is economically stable, that is, he can spend 30% of his salary on his children (this is the legal average percentage that parents must give their children for maintenance according to different laws in the world), and that he may still subsist and buy sex with prostitutes. If you do not have this economic capacity of that additional 30% of salary you must abstain from having children in order to be happy [11-16].

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